

Role of Career Women in Families

(Study of the Existence of Career Women in Families in Balunijuk Village)

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ABSTRACT

The existence of women over the time in transition or shift from traditional to modern. The role of the woman who used to be adopted only capable of working in the domestic realm, but this time she is able to develop itself in the public sphere. This raises the existence of variants of interest, between the domestic and the public sphere. This study used a qualitative research method with case study approach. The theory used in this research is by using the concept of rational choice of James Coleman. The purpose of this research is to describe the existence of a career woman in the family. These results indicate that the existence of career women in the public sphere in the family recognized for their collective agreement concluded between career women with families. Mainly deal agreed with her husband and children. But the deal does not diminish the responsibility of working women in the domestic sphere. Career woman in the village Balunijuk not neglect its role as a housewife and also as a career woman. Role between domestic and public balanced and collaborate.

Keywords: *Existence, Roles, Women Career*

I. Background

Gender equality in the last decade has experienced a transition regarding the existence of women in particular. The existence of women often experiences polemic and resistance from various parties, especially men. Women become objects that are often marginalized in people's lives in various aspects such as social, economic, cultural and political. The existence of women is often oppressed as a housewife and only able to explore themselves in the domestic realm. But this does not make women become indoctrinated with the oppression. At present, many women are found able to explore themselves not only in the domestic realm but also able to develop themselves in the realm of the public. The development and development of modernization is currently a lot of women who work outside the home. Women often have obstacles and obstacles in entering the workforce because of the oppressive factors committed by the community and the husband. Although women are given space to develop themselves in the realm of the public or the world of work. This does not eliminate the function of women in the domestic realm as housewives. This caused a dual function for women in Indonesia. The role of women today is no longer only focused on the domestic realm, but is growing in the public domain. Women who are able to enter the workforce cannot be said to ignore their responsibilities as wives and mothers. This reality cannot be fundamentally oppressed but needs an in-depth survey to prove this. Women naturally have a full function in the family, because they have a duty to protect their husbands and children.

One of the functions of women as mothers to their children is related to their child's personal growth. Child's growth is developing one of the factors that shape the child's personality is the role of a mother. Mother has an important role in shaping the personality of a child. Therefore the role of a mother in the household is needed. The problem studied in this study focuses on

career women in Balunijuk Village, Merawang District, Bangka Regency. Balunijuk Village is one of the villages in Merawang District, Bangka Regency which has an area of 5,089 km² (village data in 2016). Based on the profile of village development that Balunijuk Village is experiencing better development. Conditions that can be seen especially regarding the mindset of the community have experienced changes that are so well related to sources of livelihood. Based on information obtained in the field from informants, the Balunijuk Village Chief explained that approximately 90% of women in Balunijuk Village had various sources of livelihoods such as farmers, traders, midwives, nurses, teachers, offices. It is interesting from the focus of this study, the existence of career women in the family based on the current conditions in Balunijuk Village. The existence of career women in the family becomes the focus of an interesting study to be understood and analyze in depth and comprehensive.

Basic Theory Framework

This research focuses on the concept of one of the sociology figures, James Coleman, about rational choice theory. Rational choice theory is one theory that has an important influence in people's lives, especially in contemporary sociology studies (Ritzer, 2004). According to Coleman the orientation of rational choice theory has a basic idea that "people take action intentionally with the intention of aiming at a goal, the goal is shaped by the values and choices they want to achieve" (Coleman, 1990). Individuals carry out these actions in order to realize the objectives to be achieved such as maximizing optimal function, profit and fulfillment of needs. Rational choice theory is centered on an actor and also resources in achieving the goals of his choice. Meanwhile rational choices require individuals to be able to carry out social control and follow the prevailing norms and be agreed upon together. Social control and agreement can be carried out jointly from both the individual himself and others (in this context between wife, husband and

family). The rational choice used in this study refers to how rational choices made by career women entering the public sphere influence their existence in the family. The existence of career women who are involved in the public sphere often gets bad oppression from the public. This will have an impact on their role in the family, especially in their relationship with their husbands and children. Role is something that is dynamic in accordance with social conditions. Roles relate to a person's social status which can change depending on certain social conditions or situations (Aida Vitalaya, 2010). Career women in families have multiple roles or interpreted as more than one role. The role that is meant by women does not only have a role in the public sphere but also has a role in the domestic realm as a housewife (Rustiani, 1996). Women who ventured to explore themselves in the public domain for family economic development, are required to continue to understand their nature as women who always carry out their functions as housewives and wives in the family.

II. Methodology

This study uses qualitative research methods using a case study approach and performs descriptive qualitative data collection techniques through in-depth interviews. Qualitative descriptive research is a type of research that attempts to explain phenomena that occur in people's lives. In addition, revealing social problems that occur in people's lives. Data collection techniques are carried out by purposive sampling by determining the criteria of informants. The criteria for informants in this study is that the source of information is not only based on female informants who work but also the general public in providing assessments or responses regarding women who work outside the home. Because this can be a supporting data and complementary in analyzing and describing the existence of career women in the family, especially in the Balunijuk Village community, Merawang District,

Bangka Regency. In addition, the data source obtained is also in the form of documentation or village data which is a secondary or complementary data source to support the findings in the field.

III. Discussion

Gender equality is often a polemic which until now cannot be resolved from social, cultural, economic and political aspects. Women's roles are often used as objects produced by society in general, men in particular. But along with the development of the time the oppression was able to be overcome by women, especially women activists who have succeeded in providing opportunities for women to be involved not only in the domestic sphere but also in the public sphere through feminist movements against the oppression of the patriarchy and the public. One of the opportunities open to women today is in the political aspect that is given 30% of space to be able to participate in the political sphere. Therefore it is important that with the opportunity to be more open for women to be able to participate in the public domain so that they can be interpreted not only subjectively but objectively. This is so that women do not ignore their role and nature as real women in the family when they enter the public domain or work. Becoming important in this chapter is described in detail about the existence of career women in families in the Balunijuk Village community, Merawang District, Bangka Regency. Women who work in the public domain have very high sensitivity in the current kotomporer context. Negative responses often arise when women have entered the workforce, one of the negative responses that arise as a husband and wife disputes because the wife works outside the home, so the husband and children are not given good services such as wives and mothers who are generally able to take care of and provide time not limited to families. This chapter will explain the dynamics of career women in the family, especially regarding their existence in the family.

Based on the interview results from one of the informants, explained that working women were accumulated in the percentage of 90% in Balunijuk Village (village data source in 2016). The source of his livelihood also varied not only in one area. Variety of livelihoods such as farmers, traders, teachers, midwives and offices. Meanwhile women are given space to be able to participate in each village head election or run for village head. In addition, the placement of women in the village structure (financial and service aspects) is often involved to be able to participate in every village activity. According to the results of the interview with the same informant explained that there was no difference between men and women. People here, especially for men, do not feel objected if their wives are involved in public activities or work outside the home. In fact, this is very helpful for the husband in meeting the needs and improving the welfare of family life together. Based on the reality that occurs that the majority of women who work outside the home do not experience obstacles or problems with the family. This is because the support of husband or family has become the main capital for women to work and work outside the home.

Women who work outside the home certainly cannot be separated from a consensus or agreement between their wife and family, especially husband and children. Support from family, especially husband and child, is an absolute requirement for a woman to work outside the home. The support obtained is not immediately instantaneous but through a long agreement and process. Consequences become a benchmark for establishing this consensus. Based on the results of an interview from one of the female informants who worked as a midwife in Balunijuk Village explained that to get approval from the husband had to go through serious talks. His talk is related to the child's growth and development in the future. Based on the explanation of one Anggi informant who works as a midwife explained that child growth is the top

priority in deciding to be able to work outside the home, but so far the husband or family does not restrict women from doing work outside the home on daasar does not eliminate his responsibilities as a wife and mother. Likewise, family attitudes are very open and provide opportunities for women to be able to work and explore themselves and their abilities in the public space. The role of a woman who has been involved in every activity in the public sphere, does not reduce or ignore her responsibilities as wife and mother. Relationships with families do not reduce the meaning of togetherness despite spending a lot of time outside the home. This proves that the rational choices conceptualized by Coleman provide important significance and relevance. Women who work outside the home are given social control in playing their role as career women. Social control in which the norm is carried out based on mutual agreement or consensus. Coleman explained that when individuals take action using rational choices, of course with certain intentions and objectives based on the agreement of the husband or family. The same is done by women in Balunijuk Village in determining choices that are considered rational. The rational choice he does as a career woman who works outside the home is done with the intent and purpose of maximizing economic needs and family welfare. In order to help the family economy to be fulfilled optimally, not to dominate the position of the husband as the head of the household. The following is a reflection of the mapping from the explanation of Coleman's concept as follows:

Meanwhile, a fairly critical statement was acknowledged by one of the informants from Balunijuk Village who explained that it was time for women to develop themselves and abilities in the public space. Emancipation of women increasingly gets space to be able to engage in activities and activities outside the home or public. The time division between work outside the home and at home is not difficult for informants, namely Siti M as a teacher. According to him, husband and child remain the most important focus even though working outside the home, supervision is still carried out on the family as well as vice versa. Career women in this village enjoy every activity both outside the home and inside the house. The role of wife and mother is done properly and correctly without reducing the role of mother and wife in general. Every activity of the child is always supervised, because it is very important because it affects the growth of the child. In addition, every need for a husband and child is always prioritized before carrying out routine activities when going to work. In addition to carrying out dual functions as career women and housewives, various other activities were also carried out by career women in the village. Based on the findings in the field as for other activities carried out gardening, carried out every holiday with her husband and children. It is becoming increasingly interesting that the dual role of career women does not make women difficult in carrying out every obligation both as a career woman and as a housewife. Because based on the findings in the field, the presence of career women in the family is very openly accepted by families and village communities. This condition was supported by two informants namely Iwan and Hendra explaining that women who work outside the home are strongly supported by the community so that women who especially have a high education must be able to utilize and develop their abilities outside the home by working in government institutions or agencies. The current condition in Balunijuk Village regarding the existence of career

women in the family has great opportunities regarding support from family and society. The reality found in the field provides an understanding for society at large, especially for women, there is no limit to the space and time for women to be involved in developing themselves in the public domain. The dual role of women both in the domestic and public spheres is carried out in a balanced manner without reducing the meaning of the real nature of women. This condition shows that career women in Balunijuk Village in any condition are able to play their role as women who have a dual role both in the realm of domestic and public.

While the same statement from one of Muji's informants is a teacher about his existence in the family when working outside the home. The role of women after working outside the home such as taking care of children and homes has become an obligation for women who work outside the home. This condition has become a routine for informants who cannot be removed from their daily habits even in the midst of their busy life as career women outside the home. Although it has chosen to work as a career woman the responsibility as a wife and mother is a necessity that cannot be eliminated in human life. The informant explained that a mother or wife has an important role in the family such as serving her husband and children, educating children into a useful generation. Does not reduce the meaning of the existence of a husband, the informant explained that often people experience mistakes, as well as women who work outside the home. Sometimes certain times forget the important role especially regarding children's education related to the decline in school values due to negligence that is not intentionally done, especially in controlling every child's activities. In this case, the husband's duty to reprimand his wife becomes a necessity and responsibility as the head of the household. The informant acknowledges that such conditions occur during office work that cannot be controlled so that adverse effects occur in children. However, these conditions can be overcome

by the distribution of time and good and right social control. So that things went well until now.

To understand the above conditions it is important to understand that women's emancipation is not a freedom whose meaning is completely free to take action. There is social control and binding norms and are agreed together in the family. Social control and norms act as a reference for women in carrying out their duties both in the domestic and public spheres. Coleman's rational choice as a concept of thinking that has relevance to the conditions that occur in Balunijuk Village. The choice chosen by women in the village is carried out rationally and considerably based on the desires and goals to be achieved in realizing a life that is more economically prosperous. But this choice does not necessarily arise by itself, there are several factors that drive the development of self and ability and economic needs through consensus with the family. The role of women in the domestic and public spheres collaborates and is balanced without neglecting each of the responsibilities carried out. However, even though the role of career women in Balunijuk Village is running well, it is possible that if it is not strengthened by better social control between wife and husband and family there will be social problems in the family.

IV. Conclusion

The existence of career women in families in Balunijuk Village shows that there is a dual role that functions in a balanced manner both inside and outside the home. The presence of career women in the family is accepted based on agreements and norms agreed upon jointly by the family. Agreement and social control become one of the factors that causes women to be able to explore themselves in the public domain. The role of Kariri women in Balunijuk Village has a dual role both in the public and domestic realms. The dual role carried out by them outside the home makes it feel comfortable and not difficult to do. They continue to recognize that a woman's nature

remains a good wife and mother for her husband. A wife who is able to serve her husband and wife well even in the midst of busy work outside the home, is still their responsibility. Associated with people's views is very supportive for women to develop themselves and their abilities in the public sphere. Support from family and community is shown based on appreciation and attitude to career women in the village. Women in the village are given opportunities and space to be able to participate in every village activity. In addition, women are also given the opportunity to run for the village head, but so far no woman wants to run. Because they are only interested in working outside the home such as midwives, nurses, teachers, offices, farmers, and traders who according to him is the ability possessed. Although working outside the home, it does not eliminate the responsibility of being a housewife in the family. The dual role of women is actually not difficult to implement if the basis does not eliminate the true meaning of women's nature for career women in Balunijuk Village. In essence, the nature of women is actually a spirit that has been united in the soul of every woman. Even so, women have many opportunities to be involved in the public sphere in order to be able to develop themselves and their abilities.

As the informant explained that when an error was made, the husband as the head of the household must reprimand. Examples of problems that occur about children, especially the problem of education is a problem that is a top priority when it comes to learning the decline in assessment of children in school. The function of the mother in this case becomes important in relation to education, because the mother is a very important agent in determining the success of a child's education both formally and non-formally. Social control must be further enhanced in every activity carried out in order to understand the limitations in carrying out the role of a career woman outside the

home. These restrictions are the result of an agreement between the wife and family.

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Penelitian

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